

1 **Mutually exclusive expression of EZH1 and EZH2 in the human embryo in pre-implantation**
2 **development.**

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7 We describe here mutually exclusive expression of EZH1 and EZH2 in the human embryo in
8 pre-implantation development. EZH1 was expressed concomitant only with EZH2 induction suggesting a
9 non-canonical function for EZH1 during the first two cell division following fertilization in humans.

10 Citations

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